

Introduction

Welcome to the **first edition** of the Diamond OA (OA) Expertise Center's newsletter! With this quarterly newsletter we will keep you posted on the latest news from the Diamond OA community in The Netherlands and beyond. We ([Bregt](#), [Juliana](#), [Femke](#) and [Maria](#)) have been working since last year to build the foundation of the Expertise Centre, and we are happy to share with you the upcoming **Agenda for 2025**. Let us know what you think!

News & Resources

HOW TO FLIP YOUR JOURNAL: A GUIDE TO MORE EQUITABLE PUBLISHING WITH DIAMOND OA

You may have heard of the recent mass resignation of the Journal of Human Evolution, where editors quit over a dispute with a major publishing house. A new spin-off journal is "[a possibility](#)." We hope that the editorial board reads the guide '[How to flip your journal](#)' to Diamond OA written by OA experts from Dutch universities. This lavish guide highlights resources for **editors**, gives examples of **success stories** of journals switching to a Diamond OA model, **expected costs** as well as **funding models**. A must-read for anyone who is an (aspiring) editor and wishes to change their journal to a more equitable publishing model!

DIAMOND OA STANDARD (DOAS): SELF-ASSESSMENT TOOL FOR PUBLISHERS AND SERVICE PROVIDERS

If you are a Diamond OA publisher or service provider, we strongly recommend following the **Diamond OA Standard (DOAS)** developed within the **DIAMAS project** which provides an overview of standards and best practices categorized by "required" and "desired" items. The **first step is to fill in this self-assessment tool** and start a **discussion with your editorial team**. This tool can provide you with focus areas to help develop your publishing activities: from finance, governance, publishing operations, peer review, technical efficiency to equity, diversity and inclusion. The expertise center aims to start discussions with publishers and service providers in the Netherlands on topics which can be improved after the DOAS-self-evaluation. **If you want us to organize a session regarding the self-assessment tool or need support, please contact us.**

AMBASSADORS CALL FOR DIAMOND OA

The Diamond OA Expertise Center is looking for researchers who want to act as ambassadors for Diamond OA. These will be **actively involved in promoting Diamond OA publishing and closely collaborate with the Expertise Center**. Read more about the call and how to apply [here](#). The deadline to apply is **April 4th**.

CO-CREATION EVENT TO DEVELOP A DIAMOND OA DISCOVERY KIT

If you are struggling to find a suitable Diamond OA journal for your research or to recommend high-quality Diamond OA options to researchers you're not alone. On **May 28, 2025, at SURF in Utrecht**, we're bringing together researchers, librarians, policy advisors, and communication officers for a full-day collaborative event to develop a national Diamond OA Discovery Kit. This kit will serve as a practical resource to navigate, promote, and support Diamond OA publishing at the faculty and department levels. Attend this session to **i) gain insights from expert discussions on Diamond OA publishing; ii) participate in hands-on workshops to shape the discovery kit; iii) help design strategies to ensure effective local adoption.** Register for this free event funded by [OSNL here](#).

In the Spotlight

- [European Diamond Capacity Hub](#) was launched online in Jan 2025 and provides many resources and tools on Diamond OA. **Check it out now.**
- [Call to Commitment: A future-proof approach to OA Publishing in the Netherlands](#). You can sign this petition if you believe that investment in community-driven publishing should be taken into consideration when renewing read and publish deals.
- [Collective Action In Science Diamond](#). As a researcher in cognitive science, you can **sign the pledge committing to publishing at least one paper in a Diamond OA outlet.**
- [NWO Funding is available to flip your journal to a Diamond OA model](#). The deadline for applying is 15th of May 2025 at 14:00.

[Use this guide while preparing for the call!](#)

Please provide your **feedback** on the **Diamond OA Expertise Centre** website by answering **anonymously** to [this survey](#) (only composed of 8 questions!).

Agenda

- **May 28:** [Developing a Diamond OA Discovery Kit](#), SURF, Utrecht, NL
- **June 3:** [DIAMAS final project conference on June 3rd](#), Brussels, BE.
- **June 23-27:** [2nd CRAFT-OA Summer School for \(Diamond OA\) Journal Editors](#), Coimbra, PT
- More events can be found [here](#).

Advertise your event
by sending us an
[email](#).